

USE OF IDIOMS IN ENGLISH

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Abstract: *Development of a science as a whole and a linguistic science, in particular is connected not only to the decision of actually scientific problems, but also with features internal and foreign policy of the state, the maintenance of the state educational standards which are to the generators of progress providing social, economic society. It forms the society capable quickly to adapt in the modern world.*

Key words: *idioms, linguist, scientific-theoretical aspect, educational problems.*

Conditions of reforming of all education system the question of the world assistance to improvement of quality of scientific-theoretical aspect of educational process is especially actually put. As President I.A.Karimov has declared in the program speech “Harmoniously development of generation a basis of progress of Uzbekistan”; “... all of us realize, that achievement of the great purposes put today before us, noble aspirations it is necessary for updating a society, today when we celebrating the 23th anniversary of the National Independence of our Motherland”. The effect and destiny of our reforms carried out in the name of progress and the future, results of our intentions are connected with highly skilled, conscious staff the experts who are meeting the requirements of time. Language is the system, phonological, lexical and grammatical which lies on the base of speaking. It is the

course which every speaker and writer has to know upon if he is to be understood by other hand, is manifestation of language, or by various speaker and writers of the given language. Thus, what we have before us, in oral on in written form, as material analyses, is always a product of speech, namely something either pronounced or written by some individual speaker or writer or, occasionally, a group of speakers or writers, there is no other way for a scholar to get the language than though its manifestation in speech.

As language teaching requires the formulation of rules which the learner has to observe if he is to speak and write the language correctly practical grammars, written both by speakers of the language in question and, by foreigners tend to be excessively strict, in laying down what is “inadmissible” in the language. The resent article deals with analyses of the structural, semantic and functional aspects of the English idioms. English idioms are colorful and one of the fascinating aspects of the English language, therefore their semantic, their denotational and usage plays great role in the vocabulary of every learner of the English language. At the sometime they are difficult because they have unpredictable 1meanings of collocations. Idioms are frequently neglected in general dictionaries and in classroom teaching, because they are considered marginal items, which are quaint but significant. Yet research into idioms shows that they have important roles in spoken and written language as well, particularly in conveying evaluation and developing of maintaining interactions. Phraseology is one of the most interesting subjects of investigation in Modern Linguistics. Phraseology, and especially idiomatically, was investigated in a great number of researches works. But in spite of it there still exist some aspects of idiomaticity the transformations of idioms in the context and their communicative function.

The theoretical value and scientific novelty of our article are determined by the attempt to define and examine the communicative functions of idioms on the material of the literary texts and some dictionaries. The phraseology deals with word groups consisting of two or more words whose combination is integrated as a unit with a specialized meaning of the whole such as *at the eleventh hour, bad-mouth, be fed up with, beat around the bush, coach potato, in the black, in the stock, keep an eye on, lend someone hand, lose track of, make up one mind* and so on, stability of such word groups viewed in terms of statistical probability of co-occurrence for the member words of has been offered as a reliable criterion helping to distinguish set expressions from free phrases with variable context. The article has received its heading because of great ambiguity of terms phraseology and idioms accepted in our linguistics. Opinions differ as to how this part of vocabulary should defined, classified, described and analyzed. The word “phraseology” for instance, has very different meanings in this country and in Great Britain or United States. In our linguistic literature the term has come to be used for the while ensemble of expression where the meaning of one element is depend on the other, irrespective of the structure and properties of the unit; with other authors it denotes only such set expressions which, as distinguished from idioms, do not possess expressiveness or emotional coloring and also vice versa; only those that are imaginative, expressive and emotional: N.Namosova overcomes the subjective ness of the two last mentioned approaches when she insists on the terms being applicable only to what she calls fixed context units, units in which it is impossible to substitute any of the components without changing the meaning not only of the whole unit but also of the elements that remain intact O. S Ahmatova has repeatedly insisted on the semantic integrity of their elements A. V Koonin lays stress on the structural separateness of elements in a phase logical

units, on the change of meanings in the whole as compared with its elements taken separately and on a certain minimum stability.

To sum up, all these authors use some words “phraseology” to denote the branch of linguistics studying the word-groups they have in mind. Continued intelligent devotion to the problems of phraseology of such scholars as N Namasova, A V Koonin and many others has turned phraseology into a full-fledged Linguistic discipline.

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